

Recommendation 13:

Using 'API Economy' to meet the societal need 'Faster and transparent access to public sector services'

Actual solutions and services:

Today, APIs play a central role in integrating companies with providers, suppliers and customers. API economy related to PS services refers mainly to the public sector itself releasing open data which in turn can be consumed by businesses through APIs to provide value to citizens and potentially earn some revenue.

Everyday uses of this can be businesses that want to access traffic data to find opportunities for marketing (e.g. to people stuck in traffic). Infrastructure planning and zoning are also potential consumers of this data. Population and census data can be made available via APIs for outside developers to access and use in their Apps in creative ways.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of applications pertaining to different domains • Reliability and user friendliness • Speed of new developments • Reusability • Efficiency and automation of work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming knowledge required • Poor or badly written APIs • Associated costs (development costs, maintenance costs, API documentation, support provision to users of the API) • Maintenance required • Potential of system crash when testing APIs • No standardised documentation
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design of innovative online services for citizens and businesses • Cross-sector integration • More integrated user experience • Entrepreneurship and innovation acceleration • Exposure of Public Data and Services to third parties • Personalization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security exposure / security concerns - API vulnerabilities may be used by hackers • Improper use of APIs by third parties • High utilisation of Public Sector infrastructures

Faster and transparent access to public sector services:

The sub needs under this header include: trust in governance, access to timely and accurate information, unlink Public Sector and politics.

The time frame in which the public sector is required to respond tends to shorten to meet government imperatives and citizen and stakeholder demands. A transparent public sector is an essential element of a free and democratic society. Information from a wide variety of sources must be accessed and presented to citizens in an intuitive, easy to use fashion. In addition, the public sector should strive to provide an easy way for citizens to retrieve a wide variety of documents.

Our informants said: "Public Authorities already know my social situation, why should I investigate the social benefits I am entitled to? Make citizen's life easier"

API Economy:

*The API Economy refers to the trend of turning a business or organization into a platform by using Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) to integrate and connect people, places, systems, data, things and algorithms, create new user experiences, share data and information, authenticate people and things, enable transactions and algorithms, leverage third-party algorithms, and create new product/services and business models, thus positively affecting the organization's profitability**

* Smarter with Gartner, Welcome to the API Economy, <http://www.gartner.com/smarterwithgartner/welcome-to-the-api-economy/>